

Quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) studies on anti-HIV-1 and cytotoxic arylpyrrolylsulfones

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QSAR studies of anti-HIV-1 and cytotoxic arylpyrrolylsulfones (1-51) have been discussed. The cytotoxicity of these compound is found to be dominantly controlled by electronic and hydrophobic factors whereas anti-HIV-1 activity is controlled by steric factor. Significant correlations have been obtained between cytotoxicity and equalized electronegativity X_{eq} , partition coefficient P , and anti-HIV-1 activity with molecular connectivity $^1\chi^b$.

Human immunodeficiency virus type-1 is the causative agent of acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) which is one of the most serious health problems¹. Since reverse transcriptase (RT) is an essential enzyme for the replication² of HIV, it is the most favoured target for the antiviral chemotherapy against HIV infection³. 3'-Azido-2',3'-dideoxythymidine (AZT)^{4,5}, 2',3'-dideoxyinosine (DDI)⁷, 2',3'-dideoxycytidine (DDC)⁸ and 2',3'-dideoxythymidine (DT4)⁹ are the well-known potent nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors that have found clinical use but unfortunately they produce serious side-effects such as bone marrow suppression⁶. The search for a more effective and less toxic agent has brought into focus potent yet structurally different non-nucleoside HIV-1 reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs), such as 1-[(2-hydroxyethoxy)methyl]-6-phenylthio]thymine (HEPT)¹⁰, tetrahydroimidazo[4,5,1-*k*][1,4]benzodiazepin-2(1*H*)one (TIBO)¹¹, bis(heteroaryl)-piperazines (BHAP)¹² etc. Artico *et al*¹³ reported synthesis of fiftyone derivatives of arylpyrrolylsulfones that act as anti-HIV-1 and cytotoxic agents. The family of tricyclic derivatives related to nevirapine has been found active against HIV-1 in the nanomolar range. New pyrrolyl-arylsulfones are the result of further development of pyrrole analogs¹⁴ of nitrophenylphenylsulfones (NPPS)¹⁵. Nitrophenylphenylsulfone is a potent member of a new emerging class of NNRTI agents.

We report here the correlation of cytotoxicity and anti-HIV-1 activity of pyrrolylsulfones with physicochemical parameters with a view to provide a better rational approach for the design of potent drugs. The electronic parameter X_{eq} (equalized electronegativity), hydrophobic parameter $\log P$ and steric parameter $^1\chi^b$ (first order of molecular connectivity) have been used in order to assess the role of electronic nature, hydrophobicity and molecular size of the drug molecules on the activity. The values of X_{eq} were calculated as suggested by Pauling¹⁶, $\log P$ as suggested by Nys and

Rekker¹⁷ and $^1\chi^b$ as defined by Kupchik¹⁸. The regression analysis was performed with the help of statistical package MSTAT.

Results and Discussion

Arylpyrrolylsulfones (1-51) and their cytotoxicity $\log(1/CC_{50})$, anti-HIV-1 $\log(1/EC_{50})$ activity data are listed in Table 1 alongwith the values of physicochemical parameters; CC_{50} refers to compound dose (μm) required to reduce the viability of mock infected cells by 50% and EC_{50} refers to compound dose (μm) required to achieve 50% protection of MT4 cells from HIV-1 induced cytopathogenicity. The autocorrelation among the physicochemical parameters for both cytotoxicity and anti-HIV-1 activity are shown in the correlation matrices in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively.

The correlation of cytotoxicity $\log(1/CC_{50})$ with X_{eq} gave moderate quality regression eqn.(1),

$$\log(1/CC_{50}) = 11.772 (\pm 2.034) X_{eq} - 27.748 \quad (1)$$

$$n = 33, r^2 = 0.519, S = 0.498, F_{(1,31)} = 33.489$$

where, n represents the number of data points, r is the correlation coefficient, S the standard error of estimation, F the variance ratio between the calculated and observed activities, and data with $\pm$ sign in parenthesis are standard errors of the regression coefficients. Eqn. (1) accounts for 51.9% of variance and F -ratio value was also found to be significant at 99% level [$F_{(1,31)} = 7.56$].

Correlation level was found to improve significantly when electronic parameter X_{eq} and $\log P$ were taken together,

$$\log(1/CC_{50}) = 12.161 (\pm 1.829) X_{eq} + 0.176 (\pm 0.060) \log P - 28.959 \quad (2)$$

$$n = 33, r^2 = 0.626, S = 0.445, F_{(2,30)} = 25.08$$

Note

Table 1. Biological activities and physicochemical data for various pyrrolylsulfones

Comd. no.	X	Y	Z	W	X_{eq}	$^1\chi^b$	$\log P$	$\log (1/CC_{50})$			$\log (1/EC_{50})$	
								Obs.	Cal. Eq. (3)	Cal. Eq. (4)	Obs.	Cal. Eq. (5)
1	NO ₂	H	H	H	2.495	4.792	0.662	1.444	1.274	1.246	-	-
2	NH ₂	H	H	H	2.382	4.517	-0.310	0.643	0.441	0.238	-	-
3	NO ₂	H	H	COOCH ₃	2.511	5.757	0.985	-	-	-	2.302	1.764
4	NH ₂	H	H	COOCH ₃	2.515	5.462	1.547	-	-	-	1.658	1.693
5	NO ₂	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.482	6.344	1.525	-	-	-	1.824	1.904
6	NH ₂	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.415	6.049	0.555	-	-	-	2.000	1.834
7	NH ₂	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.438	6.007	2.495	0.851	0.854	0.964	1.569	1.823
8	Cl	H	H	COOH	2.495	5.031	1.630	-	-	-	0.608	1.589
9	Cl	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.454	5.957	1.925	0.880	0.972	1.038	1.887	1.811
10	F	H	H	CONH cyclohexyl	2.386	8.075	2.505	0.532	0.471	0.544	-	-
11	F	H	H	CONHCH ₂ phenyl	2.422	7.582	1.885	-	-	-	1.398	2.201
12	F	H	H	CONH cyclopropyl	2.435	6.575	0.795	0.523	0.832	0.774	-	-
13	F	H	H	CO(NH) ₂ CHO	2.509	5.708	-3.925	0.532	1.377	0.914	-	-
14	F	H	H	COCH ₃	2.488	5.645	0.540	1.000	1.223	1.178	2.699	1.737
15	NO ₂	H	H	H	2.531	4.928	1.370	1.824	1.540	1.606	-	-
16	NO ₂	Cl	H	H	2.437	4.633	0.400	1.125	0.847	0.752	-	-
17	NH ₂	Cl	H	COOCH ₃	2.464	5.598	0.725	0.606	1.046	1.002	-	-
18	NH ₂	Cl	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.465	6.480	2.235	-	-	-	1.824	1.937
19	NO ₂	Cl	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.440	6.205	1.265	0.624	0.869	0.860	-	-
20	NH ₂	Cl	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.493	6.623	3.225	2.302	2.183	2.276	-	-
21	NO ₂	Cl	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.465	6.348	2.225	-	-	-	1.921	1.905
22	NH ₂	Cl	Cl	H	2.531	4.928	1.370	2.699	2.463	2.403	-	-
23	NO ₂	H	Cl	H	2.437	4.653	0.400	0.783	0.847	0.752	1.023	1.499
24	NH ₂	H	Cl	COOCH ₃	2.494	5.873	1.695	1.921	2.191	2.135	2.000	1.791
25	NO ₂	H	Cl	COOCH ₃	2.464	5.598	0.725	-	-	-	3.744	3.536
26	NH ₂	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.465	6.480	2.235	1.921	1.977	1.953	-	-
27	NO ₂	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.440	6.205	1.265	-	-	-	3.853	3.628
28	NH ₂	H	Cl	COOC ₃ H ₇	2.482	6.980	2.775	2.000	2.102	2.143	-	-
29	NO ₂	H	Cl	COOC ₃ H ₇	2.420	6.750	1.805	0.959	0.721	0.751	3.657	3.802
30	NH ₃	H	Cl	COOC ₃ H ₇	2.482	6.874	2.755	-	-	-	1.523	2.031
31	NO ₂	H	Cl	COOC ₃ H ₇	2.420	6.599	1.785	-	-	-	3.853	3.776
32	NH ₂	H	Cl	COOCH ₂ CH=CH ₂	2.508	6.589	2.225	2.367	2.294	2.300	-	-
33	NO ₂	H	Cl	COOCH ₂ CH=CH ₂	2.442	6.314	1.255	1.000	0.883	0.876	3.397	3.708
34	NH ₂	H	Cl	COOCH ₂ phenyl	2.484	7.747	3.245	0.523	1.193	1.409	-	-
35	NO ₂	H	Cl	COOCH ₂ phenyl	2.428	7.747	2.275	-	-	-	0.824	2.175
36	NH ₂	H	Cl	COO(CH ₂) ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	2.444	8.570	2.757	1.523	0.898	1.038	-	-
37	NO ₂	H	Cl	COO(CH ₂) ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	2.369	8.295	1.787	0.791	0.544	0.555	1.921	2.372
38	NH ₂	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.420	6.636	2.005	0.523	0.721	0.694	-	-
39	NHCH ₃	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.404	7.158	2.545	0.523	0.603	0.694	-	-
40	NH ₂ C ₂ H ₅	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.462	6.626	0.015	-	-	-	3.000	1.972
41	NHCHO	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.442	7.091	1.525	-	-	-	3.000	2.083
42	NHCOCH ₃	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.424	7.651	2.065	-	-	-	3.000	2.281
43	NHCOC ₂ H ₅	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.443	8.684	2.225	0.538	0.891	0.981	2.586	2.466
44	NHCOCH ₂ -COOC ₂ H ₅	H	Cl	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.443	8.684	2.225	0.538	0.891	0.981	2.586	2.466
44	NO ₂	H	CH ₃	COOCH ₃	2.459	6.754	2.065	-	-	-	2.009	2.003
45	NH ₂	H	CH ₃	COOCH ₃	2.398	6.479	1.095	-	-	-	2.770	1.937
46	Cl	H	NO ₂	H	2.527	4.928	1.370	2.699	2.699	2.699	-	-
47	Cl	H	NH ₂	H	2.446	4.653	0.400	1.041	0.913	0.825	-	-
48	Cl	H	NO ₂	COOCH ₃	2.541	5.873	1.695	1.921	1.613	1.719	-	-
49	Cl	H	NH ₂	COOCH ₃	2.466	5.598	0.725	0.824	1.060	1.018	1.125	1.725
50	Cl	H	NO ₂	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.509	6.480	2.235	2.222	1.377	1.513	-	-
51	Cl	H	NH ₂	COOC ₂ H ₅	2.440	6.205	1.265	1.143	0.869	0.860	-	-

Eqn. (2) accounts for 62% of variance. The value of F was also found to be significant at 99% level [$F_{(2,30)} = 5.39$].

Table 2 Correlation matrix among the parameters used for cytotoxicity $\log(1/CC_{50})$ of compounds

	X_{eq}	${}^1\chi^b$	$\log P$
X_{eq}	1 000		
${}^1\chi^b$	-0 326	1 000	
$\log P$	-0 073	0 556	1 000

Table 3. Correlation matrix among the parameters used for anti-HIV-1 activity $\log(1/EC_{50})$ of compounds

	X_{eq}	${}^1\chi^b$	$\log P$
X_{eq}	1 000		
${}^1\chi^b$	-0 519	1 000	
$\log P$	-0 074	0 496	1 000

In order to study the effect of specific substituents at X and Z positions of phenyl ring, two indicator parameters, Ind 1 for compounds possessing NO_2 at X and Cl at Z and Ind 2 for those having Cl at X and NO_2 at Z, were introduced. The resulting equations are

$$\log(1/CC_{50}) = 7.372 (\pm 1.650) X_{eq} + 0.924 (\pm 0.176) \text{Ind 1} + 1.89 (\pm 0.381) \text{Ind 2} - 17.119 \quad (3)$$

$$n = 33, r^2 = 0.772, S = 0.354, F_{(3,29)} = 32.655$$

$$\log(1/CC_{50}) = 8.086 (\pm 1.612) X_{eq} + 0.097 (\pm 0.049) \log P + 0.796 (\pm 0.179) \text{Ind 1} + 1.125 (\pm 0.364) \text{Ind 2} - 18.991 \quad (4)$$

$$n = 33, r^2 = 0.800, S = 0.337, F_{(4,28)} = 27.994$$

Eqns. (3) and (4) account for 77.2 and 80% of variance respectively. The values of F are also found to be significant for both equation at 99% level [$F_{(3,29)} = 4.51, F_{(4,28)} = 4.02$]. On the basis of the above regression analysis it can be inferred that both electronic (X_{eq}) and hydrophobic ($\log P$) factors having positive sign play important role in determining the cytotoxicity. This shows that with an increase or

decrease of electronegativity and hydrophobicity of the compounds, cytotoxicity will also increase or decrease accordingly. So less electronegative and less hydrophobic substituents would be preferred to design the less cytotoxic drugs. The regression coefficient values of Ind 1 and 2 for eqns. (3) and (4) are also positive suggesting that Cl or NO_2 group at either X or Z position (*ortho* or *meta* position) of phenyl ring do add to the cytotoxicity. Therefore, NO_2 and Cl groups at either *ortho* or *meta* position of the phenyl ring should not be preferred in future drug designing in the present series.

Correlation of anti-HIV-1 activity $\log(1/EC_{50})$ with steric (${}^1\chi^b$) and Ind 3 gave a moderate eqn. (5), where Ind 3 is the indicator parameter for compound possessing NH_2 at X, H at Y, Cl at Z and alkoxy carbonyl COOR at W position,

$$\log(1/EC_{50}) = 0.239 (\pm 0.128) {}^1\chi^b + 1.811 (\pm 0.031) \text{Ind 3} + 0.383 \quad (5)$$

$$n = 28, r^2 = 0.604, S = 0.609, F_{(2,25)} = 19.046$$

Eqn. (5) accounts for 60.4% of variance and the value of F is found to be significant at 99% level [$F_{(2,25)} = 5.57$]. The positive role of ${}^1\chi^b$ shows that large substituents may enhance the anti-HIV-1 potency. The positive value of Ind 3 in eqn. (5) indicates that NH_2 at *ortho* and Cl at *meta* in the phenyl ring and COOR (alkoxycarbonyl) at W position of pyrrole ring are important groups in determining the anti-HIV-1 activity. This unique combination of the substituents may be retained in future drug designing to obtain more potent HIV-1 drugs in this series.

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